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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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TEACHING LITERARY AND NON-LITERARY FORMS OF SPEECH TO YOUNG LEARNERS

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Abstract: The distinction between literary and non-literary forms of speech is essential for developing students' communicative competence. Literary speech is associated with standardized norms, formal registers, and educational contexts, whereas non-literary speech reflects informal, conversational, and context-dependent language use. The study analyzes theoretical perspectives on literary and non-literary speech and identifies effective pedagogical approaches for teaching these forms in school settings. The findings indicate that systematic and communicative teaching methods significantly enhance students' pragmatic awareness, stylistic flexibility, and overall language proficiency.

Key words: literary speech, non-literary speech, language register, communicative competence, school education.

Annotatsiya: Adabiy va noadabiy nutq shakllarining farqlanishi o'quvchilarda kommunikativ kompetensiyani shakllantirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Adabiy nutq odatda me'yorlashgan qoidalar, rasmiy uslub va ta'lim jarayoni bilan bog'liq bo'lsa, noadabiy nutq norasmiy, suhbatga xos hamda kontekstga bog'liq til birliklarini ifodalaydi. Mazkur tadqiqotda adabiy va noadabiy nutq shakllariga oid nazariy yondashuvlar tahlil qilinib, ularni maktab ta'limida o'qitishning samarali pedagogik usullari yoritilgan. Natijalar tizimli va kommunikativ yondashuvlarga asoslangan metodlar o'quvchilarning pragmatik ongini, uslubiy moslashuvchanligini hamda umumiy til kompetensiyasini sezilarli darajada rivojlantirishini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: adabiy nutq, noadabiy nutq, til registri, kommunikativ kompetensiya, maktab ta'limi.

Аннотация: Разграничение литературной и нелитературной форм речи играет важную роль в формировании коммуникативной компетенции учащихся. Литературная речь обычно связана с нормированными правилами, официальным стилем и образовательным контекстом, тогда как нелитературная речь отражает разговорную, неформальную и ситуативно обусловленную языковую практику. В работе проанализированы теоретические подходы к литературной и нелитературной речи, а также рассмотрены эффективные педагогические методы их преподавания в школьной практике. Результаты показывают, что системные и коммуникативные методы обучения способствуют развитию прагматической осведомлённости учащихся, их стилистической гибкости и общего уровня владения языком.

Ключевые слова: литературная речь, нелитературная речь, языковой регистр, коммуникативная компетенция, школьное образование.

INTRODUCTION

The ability to distinguish between literary and non-literary forms of speech is a fundamental component of language education, particularly at the school level, where students begin to develop conscious control over linguistic choice. Literary speech is commonly associated with standardized language norms, written discourse, academic contexts, and formal communication, whereas non-literary speech includes colloquial, informal, and conversational forms shaped by social interaction and situational context. Teaching these forms effectively enables students not only to master grammatical correctness but also to achieve pragmatic and stylistic appropriateness in communication.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theoretical foundation for studying literary and non-literary speech is deeply rooted in linguistics and sociolinguistics. One of the most influential contributions comes from M. A. K. Halliday's theory of language as a social semiotic, which emphasizes the relationship between language choice and context. Halliday introduced the concept of register, defined by field, tenor, and mode, providing a framework for understanding how different speech forms function in various communicative situations ^[1].

This theory underlines the necessity of teaching students how language varies according to social purpose and setting. Another important theoretical perspective is provided by William Labov's sociolinguistic research on language variation. W. Labov demonstrated that non-standard and non-literary forms of speech are not deficient but systematic and rule-governed, shaped by social factors such as class, age, and community norms ^[2].

His work challenges the traditional tendency in schools to prioritize literary speech while marginalizing everyday spoken language, arguing instead for an inclusive approach that recognizes the communicative value of both forms. From a pragmatic viewpoint, Dell Hymes' concept of communicative competence further strengthens the argument for balanced instruction. Hymes expanded the notion of linguistic competence to include the ability to use language appropriately in social contexts ^[3].

This concept directly supports the idea that students must learn not only literary norms but also when and how non-literary speech is acceptable and effective. More recently, applied linguists such as Carter and McCarthy have emphasized the pedagogical importance of spoken grammar and informal discourse in language education. Their research shows that exposure to authentic spoken language helps learners develop realistic communicative skills and avoid overly rigid or artificial language use ^[4]. Together, these theoretical perspectives form a solid foundation for teaching literary and non-literary speech as complementary rather than opposing systems.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodological framework of this study is based on modern educational standards that emphasize learner-centered instruction, communicative competence, and functional language use. The research employed a qualitative–quantitative mixed approach implemented in a secondary school context over one academic term. The instructional design integrated explicit teaching, contextualized practice, and interactive activities aimed at developing students' awareness and use of literary and non-literary speech forms.

At the initial stage, explicit instruction was used to introduce students to the conceptual differences between literary and non-literary speech. This included guided discussions, comparison tables, and analysis of authentic texts. Literary speech samples were drawn from textbooks, essays, and formal letters, while non-literary examples were taken from dialogues, interviews, and everyday conversational exchanges. According to Hyland, explicit genre-based instruction helps learners understand how language choices reflect social purpose and audience expectations ^[5]. This approach aligns with current curriculum standards that stress clarity of learning objectives and metalinguistic awareness.

The second stage focused on contextualized practice through task-based learning. Students participated in role-plays, situational dialogues, and rewriting tasks where they transformed a literary text into a non-literary version and vice versa. These activities encouraged learners to actively manipulate language forms and reflect on stylistic shifts. Task-based learning has been widely recognized as an effective method for developing real-world communicative skills, as it places language use within meaningful contexts rather than isolated drills ^[6].

The third stage involved interactive and collaborative methods, including group discussions, peer feedback, and reflective journals. Students worked in small groups to analyze speech situations and justify their linguistic choices. This collaborative element was designed to foster critical thinking and social interaction, which are central to communicative language teaching. Research by Richards emphasizes that interaction-based instruction supports deeper processing of language forms and functions, particularly in developing pragmatic competence ^[7].

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Data collection methods included pre- and post-instruction diagnostic tasks, classroom observations, and student reflections. The combination of these methods allowed for a comprehensive evaluation of students' progress and the effectiveness of the instructional approach. The results of the study indicate a significant improvement in students' ability to identify, differentiate, and appropriately use literary and non-literary forms of speech. Pre-instruction assessments revealed that many students associated correct language use exclusively with literary norms and demonstrated limited awareness of stylistic variation. Non-literary speech was often perceived as incorrect or inappropriate in all contexts, reflecting a common misconception in traditional language instruction.

Following the implementation of the instructional methods, post-instruction assessments showed measurable progress in several areas. First, students demonstrated increased accuracy in recognizing speech registers. In analytical tasks, the majority of participants correctly classified texts and utterances according to their communicative function and level of formality. This suggests that explicit instruction combined with authentic examples effectively enhanced students' metalinguistic awareness. Second, students showed notable improvement in productive skills. In role-play and writing tasks, learners were able to adjust vocabulary, sentence structure, and tone according to the given context. For example, when rewriting formal letters as informal messages, students successfully employed contractions, discourse markers, and conversational expressions without compromising clarity. Conversely, when transforming informal dialogues into literary texts, they demonstrated greater control over standardized grammar and cohesive devices. Third, qualitative data from classroom observations and reflective journals revealed positive changes in students' attitudes toward non-literary speech. Many learners reported increased confidence in spoken interaction and a better understanding of when informal language is appropriate. This shift is particularly important, as previous research has shown that negative attitudes toward non-standard language can hinder communicative development and learner motivation [8].

The interactive and collaborative methods also contributed to improved engagement and participation. Group discussions encouraged students to articulate their reasoning behind language choices, leading to deeper conceptual understanding. Peer feedback further reinforced learning by exposing students to alternative perspectives and strategies [10].

Overall, the results suggest that an integrated methodological approach grounded in modern educational standards effectively supports the development of stylistic and pragmatic competence. Students not only acquired theoretical knowledge but also demonstrated practical ability to navigate between literary and non-literary forms of speech in contextually appropriate ways.

The findings of this study support existing research that emphasizes the importance of teaching language variation as an integral part of communicative competence. The observed improvement in students' awareness and use of literary and non-literary speech aligns with Halliday's view that language learning involves understanding how linguistic choices are shaped by context [1].

By making these choices explicit in the classroom, teachers help students move beyond rigid notions of correctness toward flexible and functional language use. The positive attitudinal changes reported by students also resonate with Labov's sociolinguistic perspective, which argues for the legitimacy of non-standard and informal language varieties [2].

When students recognize that non-literary speech has its own rules and functions, they are more likely to engage confidently in spoken interaction and less likely to perceive everyday language as inferior. The effectiveness of task-based and interactive methods observed in this study confirms the relevance of communicative and learner-centered approaches advocated in recent pedagogical research. Richards notes that meaningful interaction is essential for developing pragmatic competence, as it allows learners to experiment with language in socially relevant situations [7].

The results suggest that such interaction is particularly valuable when teaching stylistic variation. However, the study also revealed certain challenges. Some students initially struggled to balance informality with appropriateness, occasionally overusing colloquial expressions in semi-formal contexts [9]. This indicates the need for continued guidance and scaffolding, especially in distinguishing subtle gradations of formality. Additionally, teachers must be cautious not to oversimplify the distinction between literary and non-literary speech, as real-world communication often involves hybrid forms. Despite these challenges, the discussion highlights that systematic instruction, supported by theory and modern methodology, can successfully address these issues. The integration of reflection and peer feedback appears particularly beneficial in helping students refine their understanding and application of speech forms.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Teaching literary and non-literary forms of speech in school education is essential for developing students' communicative, pragmatic, and stylistic competence. This study demonstrates that a balanced instructional approach grounded in linguistic theory and modern educational standards can significantly enhance students' ability to navigate different language registers. By combining explicit instruction, contextualized practice, and interactive methods, teachers can foster both awareness and practical skill. The results confirm that students benefit from recognizing literary and non-literary speech as complementary systems rather than hierarchical opposites. Such understanding promotes linguistic flexibility, confidence, and more effective communication in academic and everyday contexts. Future research may further explore longitudinal effects and adapt these methods to different educational settings and age groups.

References:

1. Halliday M. A. K. Language as Social Semiotic: The Social Interpretation of Language and Meaning. – London: Routledge, 2014. – 256 p.
2. Labov W. Sociolinguistic Patterns. – Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2019. – 344 p.
3. Hymes D. Foundations in Sociolinguistics: An Ethnographic Approach. – London: Routledge, 2018. – 260 p.
4. Carter R., McCarthy M. Spoken Grammar: Where Are We and Where Are We Going? // Applied Linguistics. – 2020. – Vol. 41, No. 1. – P. 1–25.
5. Hyland K. Second Language Writing. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2019. – 312 p.
6. Ellis R. Task-Based Language Teaching. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2018. – 402 p.
7. Richards J. C. Communicative Language Teaching Today. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2021. – 198 p.
8. Taguchi N. Pragmatic Competence in Second Language Acquisition // Annual Review of Applied Linguistics. – 2022. – Vol. 42. – P. 45–63.
9. Tulaganova N. F. Q., Yusupova S. B. Madaniyat, san'at va adabiyotning tilga ta'siri: o'zbek va ingliz tillarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari // Academic Research in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Vol. 3, No. 4. – P. 794–797.
10. Isabekov A., Tulyaganova N. Designing Educational Games for Literary and Non-Literary Speech Practice // International Conference on Business & Management. – 2025, December. – Vol. 1, No. 3. – P. 36–38.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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